

Studies on 6-Hydroxycoumarin

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6-Hydroxycoumarin and its methyl ether have been iodinated with the formation of 5-iodo derivatives. 6-Methoxy-5-iodo derivative has also been synthesised from 6-hydroxy-5-nitrocoumarin, the structure of which has been independently proved. The iodo derivative has been subjected to the Ullmann and Rosenmund-von Braun reactions.

6-Hydroxycoumarin on iodination with iodine and iodic acid, iodine and ammonia, and iodine monochloride afforded the same monoiodo derivative to which the 5-iodo structure has been assigned for the following reasons.

The methyl ether of this iodo derivative remained unchanged on boiling with alkali. The same iodo derivative was obtained when the methyl ether of the mononitro derivative, obtained by nitrating 6-hydroxycoumarin, was reduced, diazotised, and treated with potassium iodide. The methyl ether of the mononitro derivative did not undergo any change on heating with ammonia, which eliminated the possibility of its being the 3-nitro derivative¹. The amino derivative obtained on reduction, when heated with hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube or when diazotised and boiled with sulphuric acid, furnished a compound which developed a yellow colour with alkali. It was different from 7-hydroxy-6-methoxycoumarin (scopoletin) which gave intense blue fluorescence and which was synthesised by the Elbs persulphate oxidation of 7-tosyloxycoumarin, methylation of 7-tosyloxy-6-hydroxycoumarin formed, and subsequent hydrolysis of the tosyloxy group. This established the 5-nitro structure. Desai and Bhavsar² reported the synthesis of scopoletin by the above method, but no details are yet available.

6-Methoxycoumarin on iodination also gave the 5-iodo derivative. No higher iodo derivative of 6-hydroxycoumarin was obtained even by using excess of the iodinating agents.

6-Methoxy-5-iodocoumarin has been converted into 6,6'-dimethoxy-5,5'-bicoumarinyl by the Ullmann reaction and into 6-methoxy-5-cyanocoumarin by the Rosenmund-von Braun reaction. The cyano derivative remained unchanged on boiling with potassium hydroxide and sulphuric acid.

*EXPERIMENTAL

6-Hydroxy-5-iodocoumarin.—6-Hydroxycoumarin (1.62 g., 0.01 *M*) in ammonia (22%, 10 ml) and water (35 ml) was treated dropwise with iodine (2.54 g., 0.01 *M*) in potassium

1. Cf. Clayton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1368.

2. *Curr. Sci.*, 1951, 20, 325.

* All melting points are uncorrected.

iodide (5 g.) solution with vigorous stirring. The iodo derivative separating on addition of ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid crystallised from dilute ethanol in needles (1.5 g.), m.p. 214-45°. (Found: I, 44.12. $C_9H_5O_3I$ requires I, 44.0%).

The same product was obtained when the coumarin (1.62 g., 0.01 *M*) in warm ethanol (20 ml) was treated with iodine (1.01 g., 0.004 *M*) and iodic acid (0.4 g.) in water; the mixture was stirred for 3 hours and then diluted with water.

The same product was also obtained in slightly inferior yield when the coumarin (1.62 g., 0.01 *M*) in acetic acid (25 ml) and HCl (25 ml) was treated with iodine monochloride (1.62 g., 0.01 *M*). The mixture was left overnight at 60°, stirred vigorously for 3 hours on the next day, and diluted with water.

6-Hydroxy-5-nitrocoumarin.—6-Hydroxycoumarin (3.24 g., 0.02 *M*) in H_2SO_4 (conc., 15 ml) was slowly treated with a mixture of nitric acid and sulphuric acid (1:3) at 0° with stirring. The stirring was continued for 1 hour and the reaction mixture was added to crushed ice. The product separating was crystallised first from acetic acid and then from benzene in yellow needles, m.p. 204-205°. (Found: N, 7.30. $C_9H_5O_3N$ requires N, 6.80%).

The methyl ether was prepared by refluxing the above coumarin (1 g.) in acetone (100 ml) with dimethyl sulphate (1 ml) in presence of potassium carbonate for 12 hours and crystallised from dilute ethanol in needles, m.p. 151-52°. (Found: C, 54.38; H, 3.35; N, 5.95. $C_{10}H_7O_3N$ requires C, 54.30; H, 3.19; N, 6.37%). This compound (0.3 g.) on heating on a steam bath with liquor ammonia (22%, 20 ml) for 3 hours did not undergo any change.

6-Methoxy-5-aminocoumarin.—6-Methoxy-5-nitrocoumarin (1 g.) in ethanol (5 ml) was heated under reflux for 2 hrs. with stannous chloride solution. Excess of ammonia was then added and the reaction mixture extracted repeatedly with ether. The product obtained on removal of the ether crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in shining yellow needles, m.p. 157-58°. (Found: C, 62.89; H, 4.60; N, 7.56. $C_{10}H_9O_3N$ requires C, 62.84; H, 4.82; N, 7.33%).

6-Methoxy-5-hydroxycoumarin.—The above aminocoumarin (0.2 g.) was heated in a sealed tube with 2.5*N*-HCl (30 ml) at 150-60° for 3 hrs. The product obtained on extraction with ether crystallised from benzene-ethanol-petroleum ether mixture in shining yellow needles, m.p. 241-42°. It dissolved in sodium hydroxide to form a yellow solution.

The same product was obtained when the aminocoumarin (0.1 g.) was diazotised and the solution was treated with 30% H_2SO_4 (20 ml). (Found: C, 62.82; H, 4.26. $C_{10}H_9O_4$ requires C, 62.50; H, 4.20%).

6-Methoxy-5-iodocoumarin.—6-Methoxy-5-aminocoumarin (0.3 g.) in HCl (conc., 6 ml) at 0° was treated gradually with ice-cold sodium nitrite (0.35 g.) solution. The reaction mixture was added dropwise to an ice-cold potassium iodide (0.5 g.) solution. The product separating on keeping the reaction mixture at room temperature for 3 hrs. was treated with sodium bisulphite solution and crystallised first from dilute ethanol and then from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in needles, m.p. 148-50°. The mixed m.p. with the methyl ether of 6-hydroxy-5-iodocoumarin, prepared as usual with dimethyl sulphate and

potassium carbonate, was not depressed. (Found: C, 39.52; H, 2.66; I, 42.48. $C_{10}H_7O_3I$ requires C, 40.00; H, 2.50; I, 42.30%).

The same product was obtained when 6-methoxycoumarin (1.76 g., 0.01 *M*) was iodinated with iodine monochloride (1.62 g., 0.01 *M*) in acetic acid (10 ml) as above.

7-Tosyloxycoumarin.—7-Hydroxycoumarin (4.9 g.) in acetone (100 ml) was treated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (6 g.) followed by gradual addition of sodium bicarbonate (4 g.) solution. After vigorous stirring for 4 hours, the reaction mixture was poured into water. The product separating, after washing with NaOH solution, crystallised from dilute ethanol in thin plates (4.5 g.), m.p. 148-49°. (Found: C, 60.68; H, 4.04. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3S$ requires C, 60.75; H, 3.79%).

6-Hydroxy-7-tosyloxycoumarin.—7-Tosyloxycoumarin (3.3 g.), dissolved in pyridine (75 ml), was mechanically stirred and KOH (8 g.) solution was added, followed by potassium persulphate (8 g.) in water (200 ml) during 3 hrs. Next day the solution was just acidified and the paste separating was removed. The solution was washed with ether and heated with HCl (100 ml) on a steam bath for 45 mins. The separated solid crystallised from dilute ethanol in thin plates (0.2 g.), m.p. 203-204°. The original product (1g.) was recovered from the paste obtained on acidification. (Found: C, 57.76; H, 3.60. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6S$ requires C, 57.89; H, 3.61%).

Methyl Ether.—The above coumarin (0.5 g.) in acetone (100 ml) was refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (0.3 ml) for 8 hrs. The product obtained on working up as usual was crystallised from acetic acid in cubes, m.p. 195-96°. (Found: C, 59.13; H, 4.03. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6S$ requires C, 58.95; H, 4.04%).

7-Hydroxy-6-methoxycoumarin (Scopoletin).—The above methyl ether (0.3 g.) was dissolved in H_2SO_4 (conc., 10 ml) and kept overnight. The solid obtained on pouring over crushed ice was crystallised from water in needles, m.p. 203-204°. This was prepared previously by a number of workers by different methods^{3,4} who recorded melting points 204° and 202° respectively. (Found: C, 62.60; H, 4.25. Calc. for $C_{10}H_8O_4$: C, 62.50; H, 4.25%).

6,6'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-bicoumarinyl.—6-Methoxy-5-iodocoumarin (3.02 g., 0.01 *M*), dissolved in dry diphenyl ether (20 ml), was refluxed on a wire gauze with copper bronze (1.8 g., 0.03 *M*) for 3 hrs. The mixture was filtered hot and the filtrate cooled and diluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). The product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in thick needles (0.5 g.), m. p. 292°. (Found: C, 68.21; H, 4.11. $C_{20}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 68.60; H, 4.10%).

6,6'-Dihydroxy-5,5'-bicoumarinyl.—The above bicoumarinyl (0.5 g.) in acetic anhydride (9 ml) was heated with hydriodic acid (9 ml, *d* 1.7) at 130-40° for 2 hrs. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in cold sodium bisulphite solution was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 395-96°. (Found: C, 67.41; H, 3.61. $C_{18}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 67.10; H, 3.10%).

6-Methoxy-5-cyanocoumarin.—An intimate mixture of 6-methoxy-5-iodocoumarin (3.02 g.) and anhydrous cuprous cyanide (1.78 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 200-10° for

3. Head and Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1241.

4. Seka and Kallir, *Ber.*, 1931, 64B, 909.

half an hour. The solid was powdered and extracted with acetone. The product from acetone extract was crystallised from acetic acid in needles (1 g.), m.p. 188-89°. It remained unchanged on boiling with aqueous or ethanolic KOH solution (10% and 20%) or with 90% H_2SO_4 . (Found: C, 65.42; H, 3.75; N, 7.25. $C_{11}H_7O_3N$ requires C, 65.67; H, 3.50; N, 6.96%).

6-Hydroxy-5-cyanocoumarin.—The above cyanocoumarin was heated at 130-40° in acetic anhydride (9 ml) with hydriodic acid (9 ml, d 1.7). The product obtained was crystallised from dilute ethanol in needles, m.p. 274-75°. (Found: C, 64.57; H, 2.80; N, 6.94. $C_{10}H_5O_3N$ requires C, 64.18; H, 2.67; N, 7.50%).

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